

VOLLEYBALL PLAYERS' JUMPING ABILITY AND ITS RELATIONSHIP WITH OTHER KINEMATIC FACTORS

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Abstract: This article scientifically and methodologically analyzes the jumping ability characteristic of volleyball players and its interrelation with other kinematic factors. During the study, the influence of jumping ability on the effectiveness of technical and tactical movements in volleyball was examined, especially its significance in attacking hits, blocking, jump setting, and jump serving. The article also analyzes modern methods of developing jumping ability and jump endurance in the process of special physical training of volleyball players, the stages of forming these qualities in young volleyball players, and the effectiveness of exercises and methodologies aimed at improving jumping performance.

Keywords: Volleyball, jumping ability, jump endurance, speed-strength quality, biomechanics, coordination, aerodynamics, explosive strength, special physical training, attacking hit, blocking, technical-tactical training, young volleyball players, jumping technique, sports mastery.

Human motor activity, its volume, intensity, coordination, and effectiveness are ultimately determined by the proportional development of all physical qualities. Therefore, regardless of the purpose, essence, and content of a movement or the type of sport to which it belongs, its execution at a certain intensity is interconnected with all physical qualities. In turn, each physical quality, for example the rate of jumping ability, is determined by the proportional development of other physical qualities. In volleyball, for instance, jumping from a standing position or after an approach run to perform an attacking hit from a specific zone is based on simple reaction, movement speed, the absolute and explosive strength of the legs, the rapid inertial force of the trunk and arms, and aerodynamic force. In addition, repeated jumping during the game requires jump endurance, agility for moving from one zone to another to perform attacks or blocks, and flexibility for bending and rapidly extending the trunk during attacking actions and powerful jump hits.

The increasing intensity of modern volleyball, the rapid movement of six players within a relatively small area (9×9 m), the quick transition from one game action to another, and the growing competition require not only highly developed physical qualities in proportional relation but also well-developed psychological qualities such as attention, memory, perception, thinking, awareness, rapid situational recognition, differentiation, and decision-making. For this purpose, psychofunctional capabilities must be systematically developed through specific exercises. Only then can quality and efficiency in all jump-executed game techniques be achieved, allowing players to complete actions successfully.

According to many sports scientists, emphasizing the coordination, biomechanical, and aerodynamic characteristics of jumping is of great practical importance in teaching and improving volleyball-specific technical and tactical skills (Yu.D. Zheleznyak, 1998; Yu.D.

Zheleznyak, V.A. Kunyanskiy, A.V. Chachin, 2005; Yu.D. Zheleznyak, 2013; V.E. Khapko, V.P. Maslov, 1990; V.Yu. Schneider, 2008; N.V. Belyaev, L.V. Bulygin, 2004; A.V. Belyaev, M.V. Savin, 2000; Yu.N. Kleshchev, 2003; L.R. Ayropetyants, A.A. Pulatov, 2012). According to these authors, the effective execution of attacking and blocking skills requires jumping abilities that are coordinatively adapted to these game techniques.

Most game skills performed in modern volleyball, such as jump serves, jump sets, spikes, and blocks, are executed “in the air.” Therefore, the effectiveness of these skills depends not only on technical mastery but mainly on jumping ability and jump endurance. The development of these qualities has become one of the most important topics in volleyball practice and has been widely discussed in scientific studies and literature.

For example, Yu.D. Zheleznyak (1998), using vertical jumping as an example, pointed out that the “shock method” is highly effective in developing the speed-strength qualities of qualified volleyball players. According to him, this method produces excellent results in developing explosive strength, but such training sessions should be conducted three times a week 10–12 weeks before competitions.

Based on his research, Chan Suan Dong (1987) stated that the special physical qualities ensuring game effectiveness in volleyball players are determined by two factors during different stages of preparation: speed-strength training and a combined factor of speed and endurance. In the first stage, these factors account for 83.3%, with speed-strength training ranking first and speed training second. In the second stage, the показатель reaches 93.2%, and in the third stage 100%, where speed and speed endurance take first place while speed-strength training occupies second place.

According to Yu.N. Kleshchev (2003), at the initial stage of training, in addition to body height, jumping ability and agility are extremely important indicators. In later stages, speed, arm muscle strength, and attention stability become more significant.

As a result of studying the influence of physical education lessons combined with volleyball elements on the physical preparedness of primary school students, Zuoza Aureolius-Kazis Kazevich (1989) concluded that purposefully organized volleyball lessons are not only an effective means of educating young students but also provide an opportunity to select children for volleyball clubs and predict their correct specialization.

M.I. Popichev (1992), who proposed a new methodology for developing jumping ability, tested this methodology on young volleyball players. He divided the children into four groups according to the proportions of their body segments:

1. Children with short lower legs and long thighs and torso
2. Children with long thighs and short torso and short lower legs
3. Children with long lower legs and short thighs
4. Children with short thighs and long torso and lower legs

Taking these morphological characteristics into account, he applied specialized jumping exercises for each group and later evaluated the effectiveness of the training. The results showed that the best indicators in vertical jumping, take-off force, and take-off time were observed in the first group of children.

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